

Wind turbine

System Description:

The system is a wind turbine

System Requirements:

The wind turbine automatically switches to "Ready" mode when powered on.

The wind turbine generates power only when wind speed is between 15 and 90 km/h.

The wind turbine remains in "Ready" mode with blades stopped when wind speed is below 15 km/h.

The wind turbine remains in "Ready" mode with blades stopped when wind speed is above 90 km/h.

The wind turbine immediately stops blade rotation when a bird is detected within a 1 km radius.

The wind turbine immediately stops blade rotation when a system fault is detected while running.

The wind turbine immediately switches to "Need Repair" mode when a system fault is detected while running.

The wind turbine switches to "Need Repair" mode when a system fault is detected while in "Ready" mode.

The wind turbine allows only repair work to be performed while in "Need Repair" mode.

The wind turbine returns to "OFF" mode after a repair is successfully completed.

Model Test Purpose with keywords:

In dot format

The wind turbine automatically switches to "Ready" mode when powered on.

PMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S0 -> S1 [label="powerOn", style=solid]; // The wind turbine automatically switches to Ready
  S0 -> S0 [label="Sigma\powerOn", style=solid]; // Not important
  S1 -> S1 [label="Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
}
```


NMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {  
  S1 [shape=circle];  
  S0 [shape=octagon];  
  S0 -> S1 [label="powerOnStateOff", style=solid]; // The wind turbine automatically switches  
to OFF mode when powered on  
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\powerOnStateOff", style=solid]; // Not important  
  S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important  
}
```

The wind turbine generates power only when wind speed is between 15 and 90 km/h.

PMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {  
  S0 [shape=octagon];  
  S1 [shape=circle];  
  S0 -> S1 [label="windGood", style=solid]; // The wind turbine generates power only when  
wind speed is between 15 and 90 km/h  
  S1 -> S1 [label="Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important  
  S0 -> S0 [label="Sigma\windGood", style=solid]; // Not important  
}
```


NMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {  
  S1 [shape=circle];
```

```

S0 [shape=octagon];
S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\windBelowGenerate", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S1 [label="windBelowGenerate", style=solid]; // The wind turbine generates power but
the wind speed is below 15 km/h
}

```



```

digraph Automaton {
S0 [shape=octagon];
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\windAboveGenerate", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S1 [label="windAboveGenerate", style=solid]; // The wind turbine generates power but
the wind speed is above 90 km/h
S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```

The wind turbine remains in "Ready" mode with blades stopped when wind speed is below 15 km/h.

```

PMTF:
digraph Automaton {
S0 [shape=octagon];
S1 [shape=circle];

```

```

S0 -> S1 [label="windBelow", style=solid]; // The wind turbine remains in "Ready" mode with
blades stopped when wind speed is below 15 km/h
S0 -> S0 [label="Sigma\windBelow", style=solid]; // Not important
S1 -> S1 [label="Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
S0 [shape=octagon];
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 -> S1 [label="windBelowStateOff", style=solid]; // The wind turbine goes in "OFF" mode
when wind speed is below 15 km/h
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\windBelowStateOff", style=solid]; // Not important
S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```

The wind turbine remains in "Ready" mode with blades stopped when wind speed is above 90 km/h.

PMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 [shape=octagon];
S0 -> S0 [label="Sigma\windAbove", style=solid]; // Not important
S1 -> S1 [label="Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```

```

S0 -> S1 [label="windAbove", style=solid]; // The wind turbine remains in "Ready" mode with
blades stopped when wind speed is above 90 km/h
}

```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 [shape=octagon];
S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\windAboveStateOff", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S1 [label="windAboveStateOff", style=solid]; // The wind turbine goes in "OFF" mode
with blades stopped when wind speed is above 90 km/h
}

```

The wind turbine immediately stops blade rotation when a bird is detected within a 1 km radius.

PMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 [shape=octagon];
S0 -> S0 [label="Sigma\birdApproachStopBlades", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S1 [label="birdApproachStopBlades", style=solid]; // The wind turbine immediately
stops blade rotation when a bird is detected within a 1 km radius
}

```

```
S1 -> S1 [label="Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
}
```


NMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 [shape=octagon];
S0 -> S1 [label="birdApproachBladesContinue", style=solid]; // The wind turbine don't stops
blade rotation when a bird is detected within a 1 km radius
S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\birdApproachBladesContinue", style=solid]; // Not important
}
```

The wind turbine immediately stops blade rotation when a system fault is detected while running.

PMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {
S0 [shape=octagon];
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 -> S0 [label="Sigma\faultDetectedWhileGeneratingStopBlades", style=solid]; // Not
important
S0 -> S1 [label="faultDetectedWhileGeneratingStopBlades", style=solid]; // The wind turbine
immediately stops blade rotation when a system fault is detected while running
}
```

```
S1 -> S1 [label="Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
}
```


NMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 [shape=octagon];
S0 -> S1 [label="faultDetectedWhileGeneratingBladesContinue", style=solid]; // The wind turbine don't stops blade rotation when a system fault is detected while running
S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\faultDetectedWhileGeneratingBladesContinue", style=solid]; // Not important
}
```

The wind turbine immediately switches to "Need Repair" mode when a system fault is detected while running.

PMTP:

```
digraph Automaton {
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 [shape=octagon];
S0 -> S1 [label="faultDetectedWhileGeneratingNeedRepair", style=solid]; // The wind turbine immediately switches to "Need Repair" mode when a system fault is detected while running
S0 -> S0 [label="Sigma\faultDetectedWhileGeneratingNeedRepair", style=solid]; // Not important
}
```

```

S1 -> S1 [label="Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
S0 [shape=octagon];
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 -> S0 [label="\Sigma\faultDetectedWhileReadyStateOff", style=solid]; // Not important
S1 -> S1 [label="\Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S1 [label="faultDetectedWhileReadyStateOff", style=solid]; // The wind turbine
immediately switches to "OFF" mode when a system fault is detected while running
}

```

The wind turbine switches to "Need Repair" mode when a system fault is detected while in "Ready" mode.

PMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
S1 [shape=circle];
S0 [shape=octagon];
S0 -> S1 [label="faultDetectedWhileReadyNeedRepair", style=solid]; // The wind turbine
switches to "Need Repair" mode when a system fault is detected while in "Ready" mode
S1 -> S1 [label="Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
S0 -> S0 [label="\Sigma\faultDetectedWhileReadyNeedRepair", style=solid]; // Not important
}

```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\faultDetectedWhileReadyStateOff", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="faultDetectedWhileReadyStateOff", style=solid]; // The wind turbine
  switches to "OFF" mode when a system fault is detected while in "Ready" mode
  S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
}
  
```

The wind turbine allows only repair work to be performed while in "Need Repair" mode.

PMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S0 -> S1 [label="repairWhenNeedRepair", style=solid]; // The wind turbine allows only repair
  work to be performed while in "Need Repair" mode
  S0 -> S0 [label="Sigma\repairWhenNeedRepair", style=solid]; // Not important
  S1 -> S1 [label="Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
}
  
```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="generateWhenNeedRepair", style=solid]; // The wind turbine generate while
  in "Need Repair" mode
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\generateWhenNeedRepair", style=solid]; // Not important
}
  
```

The wind turbine returns to "OFF" mode after a repair is successfully completed.

PMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S0 -> S1 [label="returnToOffAfterRepair", style=solid]; // The wind turbine returns to "OFF"
  mode after a repair is successfully completed
  S1 -> S1 [label="Sigma", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S0 [label="Sigma\returnToOffAfterRepair", style=solid]; // Not important
}
  
```


NMTP:

```

digraph Automaton {
  S1 [shape=circle];
  S0 [shape=octagon];
  S0 -> S0 [label="Σ\returnToReadyAfterRepair", style=solid]; // Not important
  S0 -> S1 [label="returnToReadyAfterRepair", style=solid]; // The wind turbine returns to
  "Ready" mode after a repair is successfully completed
  S1 -> S1 [label="Σ", style=solid]; // Not important
}
  
```

Prompt for model in ModelJUnit generation:

You are a professional tester specialized in Model-Based Testing.

Generate an FSM in ModelJUnit

System Description:

The system is a wind turbine

System Requirements :

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The wind turbine immediately switches to "Need Repair" mode when a system fault is detected while running.

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The wind turbine allows only repair work to be performed while in "Need Repair" mode.

The wind turbine returns to "OFF" mode after a repair is successfully completed.

Instructions:

- States are represented as a group of variables.

- Actions the system can perform are transitions between states.

- Specify the state variables that influence transitions.

- Identify guards (conditions for actions to execute).

- Define the roles/users involved.

ModelJUnit-Specific Instructions:

- Use `@Action` for transitions and they must have no parameters.

- Guards should be methods named `[actionName]Guard()` (e.g., `loginGuard()` for `login()`).

- Example of an action with a guard:

```
...  
  
public boolean actionName1Guard() {  
    return stateVar1 == true && stateVar2 != 3;  
}  
  
@Action  
public void action1Name() {  
    stateVar3 = false;  
}  
  
public boolean actionName2Guard() {  
    return stateVar2 < 3 && stateVar3 == true;  
}  
  
@Action  
public void action2Name() {  
    stateVar2 = 5;  
}  
...
```

- The model must implement `FsmModel` with `getState()` and `reset(boolean testing)`.

- Track state variables (e.g., boolean, int) to control transitions.

Additional Requests:

- Class must be named "ModelGenerated".

- Ensure all states are reachable.

- Ensure all transitions have proper guards.

- Model error cases (e.g., invalid inputs).

- Include role-based access control if applicable.

- Optimize for test coverage (e.g., edge cases).

Some actions are not valid in all states, so you can add a guard method to say when that action is enabled. It must have no parameters and must return a boolean. The action method will only be called when its guard is true

No explanation is needed, just the code